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The Relationship Between Motivation of Sport Management Students to Participate in Physical Activities and Social Media Addiction

Abstract

This study was conducted to examine the relationship between motivation to participate in physical activities and social media addiction among sport management students. Relational screening and causal comparison model was used in the study. In our study, Physical Activity Participation Motivation Scale (PACMS) and Social Media Addiction Scale were used as data collection instruments. The population of the study consists of the students of Istanbul Gelisim University, which is located on the European side of Istanbul, and the sample consists of N=253 university students selected from this population by convenience sampling method. The analyses of the study were defined in the SPSS 25.0 package program and the relevant analyses were carried out through this program.

Keywords: Physical activity, Motivation, Social Media

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Spor Yöneticiliği Bölümü Öğrencilerinin Fiziksel Aktivitelere Katılım Motivasyonları ile Sosyal Medya Bağımlılığı İlişkisi

Öz

Bu çalışma spor yöneticiliği bölümü öğrencilerinin fiziksel aktivitelere katılım motivasyonları ile sosyal medya bağımlılığı ilişkisinin incelenmesi amacıyla yapılmıştır. Çalışmada, ilişki tarama ve nedensel karşılaştırma modelinden yararlanılmıştır. Araştırmamızda veri toplama aracı olarak Fiziksel Aktivitelere Katılım Motivasyonu Ölçeği (FAKMÖ) ve Sosyal Medya Bağımlılığı Ölçeği kullanılmıştır. Araştırmanın evrenini, İstanbul Avrupa yakasında yer alan İstanbul Gelişim Üniversitesi öğrencileri, örneklemini ise bu evren içinden kolayda örnekleme yöntemi ile belirlenen N=253 üniversite öğrencisi oluşturmaktadır. Araştırmanın analizleri SPSS 25.0 paket programına tanımlanmış ve ilgili analizler bu program aracılığıyla gerçekleştirilmiştir. Sonuç olarak spor yöneticiliği öğrencilerinin fiziksel aktivitelere katılım motivasyonları ile sosyal medya bağımlılıkları arasında negatif yönde zayıf bir ilişki olduğu tespit edilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Fiziksel Aktivite, Motivasyon, Sosyal Medya

Introduction

It is an undeniable fact that people who make physical activity a part of their lives stay healthier. According to the World Health Organization, the average person needs about 40 minutes of physical activity a day to be healthy. However, the number of steps taken and the time devoted to physical activity is decreasing every day. The fact that working conditions make individuals feel tired, the use of modern means of transportation, and the constant presence of future anxiety in working life reduce the time allocated to physical activity (Bozkurt & Tamer, 2020). Especially for children and adolescents, the narrowing of play areas in neighborhoods, turning to digital games, and not transferring games that should be carried over from the past to the present reduce the duration of play and activity (Demir & Hazar, 2018; Tekkurşun Demir & Cicioğlu, 2019).

Previously, the concepts of physical activity, warm-up, and exercise were used interchangeably, but today, exercise that occurs as a result of physical activity has begun to be defined as a subcategory of physical activity. Today, the concept of physical activity has evolved into a position that supports the physical, emotional, and mental development of individuals and is essential for a healthy life (Tekkurşun Demir & Cicioğlu, 2019). Physical

activity, which plays a very important role in having a healthy appearance, has a very important place in advancing the physiological capacity of the individual and maintaining the obtained muscle mass (Çakır & Şenel, 2017). The way to have a healthy and fit body at all times is to make sports and physical activity the center of our lives. In addition to physical appearance, physical activity is also very important for an individual's motivation and mental health (İlhan, 2010).

The dependence on the frequency of using the Internet and social media is increasing day by day. Social media, whose popularity is increasing day by day, especially among young people, has completely dominated human life. The concept of social media manifests itself in various areas such as news, communication, education, information sharing and making friends. The Internet, which touches human life through social media (Vural & Bat, 2010; Sağbaş, Ballı & Şen, 2016), brings a different dimension to socialization. It is now possible to become friends and meet each other without even seeing each other's faces. Demir (2016) stated that the Internet makes our lives easier, thanks to the many conveniences it provides. However, using social media too much has started to become addictive. After social media became addictive, problems began to arise. People began to spend most of the time they would have spent exercising on social platforms. It is thought that one of the most important reasons for the decrease in individuals' participation in physical activity in our age is the increase in time spent on social media (Çetiner, 2021). It is believed that the participation of individuals in physical activity will positively contribute to their lifestyle and health status and will take them away from the virtual world (Nord et al., 1995). In this context, the aim of the study is to examine whether the motivation of students of Istanbul Gelisim University Faculty of Physical Education to participate in physical activities has an effect on social media addiction.

Method

Below are the research model, population and sample, data collection tools and data analysis.

Research Model

This study was designed using the relational survey model among survey models. The relational survey model is a model for investigating the existence and/or degree of change of more than one variable together (Karasar, 2017). In addition to the correlational survey model, the causal comparison model (Büyüköztürk et al., 2008), which is used to determine the cause

of a naturally occurring event and the variables that affect these causes, was used. The survey method was used in the research and the study was conducted on a voluntary basis.

Population and Sample

The population of the study consists of the students of the Department of Sport Management at Istanbul Gelisim University, which is located on the European side of Istanbul, and the sample consists of N=253 university students who were selected from this population using the convenience sampling method. Convenience sampling method is a sampling method that allows data to be obtained easily and quickly (Karasar, 2017).

Data Collection Tools

The study used a personal information form, the Motivation to Participate in Physical Activities Scale (MPPAAS), and the Social Media Addiction Scale as data collection tools. The corresponding scales are described below.

Personal Information Form

The personal information form prepared by the researcher includes questions about gender, age, marital status, active participation in sports, weekly free time, and time spent on social media in a day.

Motivation to Participate in Physical Activities Scale (PPSAS)

The Motivation to Participate in Physical Activities Scale, developed by Tekkurşun Demir and Cicioğlu (2018), was created to measure the extent to which participants are motivated to participate in physical activities. There are three sub-dimensions in the 5-point Likert-type scale. It is assumed that the higher the score obtained from the scale, the higher the motivation to participate in physical activities. The personal reasons sub-dimension includes items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, the environmental reasons sub-dimension includes items 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, and the causelessness dimension includes items 13, 14, 15, 16. Items 3, 9, 13, 14, 15, 16 were reverse coded. Cronbach's alpha values of the scale were found to be between 82 and 89. Cronbach's alpha values are above the 70th range, which is sufficient to judge that the internal consistency coefficient is sufficient.

Social Media Addiction Scale

The Social Media Addiction Scale was developed by Günüş (2009), and the validity and reliability study was conducted by Çömlekçi and Başol (2019). The Social Media Addiction Scale, which consists of 7 items, is designed as a 5-point Likert type. It can be said that the higher the scores obtained from the scale, the higher the social media addiction. There are no reverse coded items on the scale. The Cronbach alpha internal consistency coefficient of the scale was found to be 0.85 (Çömlekçi & Başol, 2019).

Data Analysis

The data obtained from the personal information form and related scales were processed in the SPSS package program, and the analyses were conducted through this program. In the study, normal distribution curve, skewness kurtosis value, normal distribution curve according to histogram and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test values, which were used when the number of participants was more than 50, were analyzed. Reliability analyses were performed for the total and sub-dimensions of the scales, and as a result, "Chronbach's Alpha Coefficient" was obtained. It was assumed that the data did not show a normal distribution, and Mann-Whitney U, Kruskal-Wallis-H test, and Spearman correlation analyses were performed as statistical procedures.

Results

The evaluation tables of the data obtained in the research are given below.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the participants

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Female	46	18.2
	Male	207	81.8
	Total	253	100,0
Age	18-22	88	34.8
	23-27	75	29.6
	28-32	41	16.2
	32 and above	49	19.4

	Total	253	100,0
Marital Status	Married	104	41.1
	Single	149	58.9
	Total	253	100,0
Doing Sports	Yes	208	82.2
	No	45	17.8
	Total	253	100,0
Weekly free time	1-3 hours	106	41.9
	4-6 hours	66	26.1
	7-9 hours	48	19.0
	10 hours and above	33	13.0
	Total	253	100,0
Time spent on social media during the day	1-2 hours	46	18.2
	3-4 hours	116	45.8
	5-6 hours	50	19.8
	7 hours and above	41	16.2
	Total	253	100,0

Looking at Table 1, 18.2% of the subjects who participated in the study were female and 81.8% were male, 34.8% were 18-22 years old, 29.6% were 23-27 years old, 16.2% were 28-32 years old and 19.4% were 32 and older, 41.1% were married, 58.9% were single, 82.2% did sports regularly, while 17.8% did not have a regular sports life, 41.9% spent 1-3 hours, 26.1% 4-6 hours, 19% 7-9 hours and 13% 10 hours. 8% do not have a regular sports life, 41.9% have 1-3 hours, 26.1% have 4-6 hours, 19% have 7-9 hours and 13% have 10 hours or more of weekly free time, 18.2% spend 1-2 hours, 45.8% 3-4 hours, 19.8% 5-6 hours and 16.2% spend 7 hours or more on social media.

Table 2. Skewness kurtosis and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test significance level results of Motivation to Participate in Physical Activities Scale and Social Media Participation Scale scores

Dimensions	N	Skewness	Kurtosis	P
Individual Causes	253	-.946	.917	.000
Environmental Causes	253	-.258	-.465	.000
Causality	253	-.459	-.306	.000
Motivation to Participate in Physical Activities Scale Total Score	253	-.604	-.109	.000
Social Media Addiction Scale	253	-.640	.013	.000

Examining the results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test in Table 2, it can be seen that the values obtained from the Motivation to Participate in Physical Activities Scale and the Social Media Addiction Scale deviate from normality. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov analysis is accepted as one of the methods used to determine whether or not the data obtained have a normal distribution. As a result of examining the normal distribution curves, it was found that there were excessive deviations from normality. According to Büyüköztürk (2007), the fact that the skewness kurtosis values of the variables are in the range of ± 1 points is accepted as an extreme deviation from normality, while Tabachnick and Fidell (2013) stated that the skewness kurtosis coefficients of the variables around ± 1.5 can be accepted as a deviation from normality. As a result, since there was no normal distribution in our dataset, nonparametric tests were applied to our research group.

Table 3. Descriptive Analysis of Participants' Responses to the Motivation to Participate in Physical Activities Scale and Social Media Participation Scale

Scales	N	Min	Max	Mean \pm Sd
Individual Causes	253	8.00	30.00	22.96 \pm 4.46
Environmental Causes	253	11.00	30.00	21.37 \pm 4.05
Causality	253	6.00	20.00	14.48 \pm 3.17

Motivation to Participate in Physical Activities Scale Total Score	253	34.00	78.00	58.81±9.62
Social Media Addiction Scale	253	10.00	33.00	24.72±4.47

When Table 3. is examined, it was determined that the mean scores of motivation to participate in physical activities scale, personal reasons sub-dimension was 22.96±4.46, environmental reasons sub-dimension was 21.37±4.05, causelessness sub-dimension was 14.48±3.17, motivation to participate in physical activities scale total score was 58.81±9.62, and social media addiction scale total score was 24.72±4.47.

Table 4. Evaluation of participants' Motivation to Participate in Physical Activities and Social Media Participation levels according to their gender

Scales	Gender	N	Row Mean	Row Total	U	P
Individual Causes	Female	46	121.18	5574.50	4493.50	.550
	Male	207	128.29	26556.50		
Environmental Causes	Female	46	121.35	5582.00	4501.00	.561
	Male	207	128.26	26549.00		
Causality	Female	46	130.36	5996.50	4606.50	.729
	Male	207	126.25	26134.50		
Motivation to Participate in Physical Activities Scale Total Score	Female	46	121.66	5596.50	4515.50	.584
	Male	207	128.19	26534.50		
Social Media Addiction Scale	Female	46	126.51	5819.50	4738.50	.960
	Male	207	127.11	26311.50		

Examining the motivation to participate in physical activities and social media participation levels of participants according to gender variables in Table 4, it is determined that there is no statistically significant score in all sub-dimensions and total scores ($p>0.05$).

Table 5. Evaluation of participants' motivation to participate in physical activities and social media participation levels according to their ages

Dimensions	Age	N	Row Mean	sd	X ²	p	Difference
Individual Causes	18-22 ¹	88	117.82	3	3.120	.373	-
	23-27 ²	75	127.99				
	28-32 ³	41	128.70				
	32 and above ⁵	49	140.54				
Environmental Causes	18-22 ¹	88	126.83		2.632	.452	-
	23-27 ²	75	118.75				
	28-32 ³	41	126.35				
	32 and above ⁵	49	140.47				
Causality	18-22 ¹	88	126.98		2.668	.446	-
	23-27 ²	75	119.49				
	28-32 ³	41	124.10				
	32 and above ⁵	49	140.97				
Motivation to Participate in Physical Activities Scale Total Score	18-22 ¹	88	123.81		3.097	.377	-
	23-27 ²	75	121.17				
	28-32 ³	41	125.07				
	32 and above ⁵	49	143.27				
Social Media Addiction Scale	18-22 ¹	88	130.73	7.046	.070	-	
	23-27 ²	75	140.03				
	28-32 ³	41	120.35				
	32 and above ⁵	49	105.93				

When analyzing the motivation to participate in physical activities and social media participation levels of participants according to their age variables in Table 5, it is determined that there is no statistically significant score in all sub-dimensions and total scores ($p>0.05$).

Table 6. The relationship between motivation to participate in physical activities and social media engagement levels

		Individual Causes	Environmental Causes	Causality	Motivation to Participate in Physical Activities Scale Total Score
Social Media Addiction Scale	r	-.103	.012	-.220**	-.113
	p	.101	.847	.000	.074

When the relationship between motivation to participate in physical activity and social media engagement levels is examined in Table 6, it is found that there is a weak negative relationship between the social media addiction scale and the individual reasons, environmental reasons, and causality subdimensions and the total score of the motivation to participate in physical activity scale.

Discussion and Conclusion

When examining the motivation to participate in physical activities and social media participation levels of participants according to gender variables, it was determined that there was no statistically significant score in all sub-dimensions and total scores ($p>0.05$). As a result of examining the motivation to participate in physical activity and social media participation levels of participants according to their gender, the lack of a statistically significant difference can be explained by some potential reasons. The fact that gender does not show a significant difference may indicate that it does not have a significant effect on physical activity motivation and social media engagement. However, these results may also indicate that other factors, such as age, education level, income level, lifestyle, or personal preferences, may influence these two factors more than differences in the gender of the participants. In addition, it can be noted that the student-athletes participated in physical activities rather than spending time on social media. When reviewing the literature, Bozkurt and Tamer (2020) concluded that the individual reasons scores of male students were significantly higher than those of female students. Based on this finding, males are more motivated to participate in physical activities. The research

results do not overlap with our findings. In another study, Demir and Cicioğlu (2019) found that there was no significant difference between the motivation of males and females to participate in physical activities. In another study, Altun (2024) found that there was no significant difference between male and female students according to gender in the social media addiction scale. The results of the research are consistent with our findings.

When the motivation to participate in physical activities and the level of social media participation of the participants were examined according to the age variables, it was found that there was no statistically significant value in all sub-dimensions and total scores. Although the age of the sport management students differs, their motivation to participate in physical activities and the time they spend on social media are similar. In general, it can be seen that students working in the fitness sector use social media a lot during their private lessons and participate in physical activities. However, this situation does not differ by age. In the literature review, Altun (2024) stated that the level of motivation to participate in physical activities did not change statistically according to the age variable of the students of the Faculty of Physical Education. The results of the research overlap with our results. In another study, Çiftçi (2018) found that the use of social media did not vary according to age. The findings of the research overlap with our findings.

When the relationship between motivation to participate in physical activity and social media participation was examined, it was found that there was a weak negative relationship between the social media addiction scale and the personal reasons, environmental reasons, and causelessness subdimensions and the total score of the motivation to participate in physical activity scale. According to the results of the research, spending too much time on social media negatively affects the motivation to participate in physical activities. In other words, as motivation to participate in physical activity increases and individuals make physical activity a central part of their lives, their use of social media decreases. In reviewing the literature, Altun (2024) found that there was a negative relationship between the motivation scale for sports participation and the social media scale. The results of the research are consistent with our findings. It is recommended that sport management students should stay away from social media as much as possible and develop studies to motivate them to participate in physical activities as much as possible. Conferences on the harms of spending too much time on social media can be organized and interview programs can be prepared. In this way, more time can be devoted to physical activity through a more balanced use of social media.

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